

Mechanism of Persulphate Decomposition in Aqueous Solution at 50° in the Presence of Methyl Acrylate in Nitrogen Atmosphere†

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The rate of thermal decomposition of potassium persulphate (KPS) in aqueous solution in the presence of methyl acrylate (MA), monomer (M) and nitrogen gas, may be written as

$$-d[S_2O_8^{2-}]/dt \propto (S_2O_8^{2-})^{1.42 \pm 0.08} \times (M)^{1.15 \pm 0.05}$$

in the concentration ranges of persulphate $(0.50-2.0) \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³ and monomer (M) $(1.328-5.313) \times 10^{-1}$ mol dm⁻³, i.e. within its solubility range under the experimental conditions. It has been suggested that persulphate ions oxidise the monomer, and water-soluble monomeric and oligomeric free radicals, $(M_j)_w$

where $j = 1$ to 30; $k_1 = 1.71 \times 10^{-6}$ s⁻¹ and $k_s = 1.23 \times 10^{-5}$ dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹, where k_1 is the rate constant of the irreversible dissociation of persulphate ion, viz. $S_2O_8^{2-} \rightarrow 2SO_4^{\cdot -}$; taking $k_{tw}, 2(M_j)_w \xrightarrow{k_{tw}}$ Polymer in the aqueous phase as 3.70×10^6 dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹, k_{10} has been estimated as 1.06×10^3 dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹.

It is believed^{1,2} that in the persulphate initiated aqueous and emulsion polymerizations of vinyl monomers, a persulphate ion ($S_2O_8^{2-}$) only produces two primary free radicals ($SO_4^{\cdot -}$), which are involved in the polymerization reactions, and thereafter it does not interfere with the polymerization reactions,

Such a mechanism predicts that

$$-d(S_2O_8^{2-})/dt \propto (S_2O_8^{2-})^1 \times (M)^0$$

which can be verified experimentally.

It was reported by Morris and Parts³ and by Brooks and Makanjuola⁴ that water-soluble vinyl monomers accelerate the thermal decomposition of persulphate ions in aqueous solutions, but they did not put forward any mechanism of the decomposition. Only very recently, we reported the mechanism of persulphate decomposition in

aqueous solutions in the presence of ethyl acrylate⁵, acrylonitrile⁶ and vinyl acetate⁷, where it was found that each monomer accelerated the decomposition of persulphate at the early stages of the reactions till the dissolved monomer in the aqueous phase was adsorbed/absorbed by the latex particles, but the extent of acceleration was a function of the nature of the monomer, and its concentration in the aqueous phase. For example, vinyl acetate brought about 20% persulphate decomposition in one hour, while ethyl acrylate did about 10% under identical experimental conditions; but in the absence of monomers, the amount of persulphate decomposed was less than 1% at 50° in one hour. At relatively higher concentrations of persulphate (10^{-2} mol dm⁻³), polyvinyl acetate was found to be oxidised by the persulphate⁷. We report here the results obtained from the thermal decomposition of KPS in aqueous solution in the presence of methyl acrylate at 50°.

Experimental

The reagents used were of AR/GR grade (B.D.H./E. Merck India/Glaxo). They were further purified by recrystallisation⁵⁻⁷. The monomer (B.D.H., England) quality was stabilised by methoxyphenol, and was purified and distilled by the

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reported method⁶. The distillate was then polymerised partially in N₂-atmosphere with little benzoyl peroxide (0.05%, w/v) and fractionated immediately in vacuum⁷. The refractive index of the middle fraction at 20–25° was found to be 1.4020 in agreement with the reported value⁹ and it was used for the present investigation. The monomer was also processed by fractional distillation over copper acetate using a Vigreux column and a reflux-head under nitrogen atmosphere. Almost identical results were obtained by using the MA purified by the two different methods. Incidentally, it may be noted that Morris and Parts⁸ purified MA (of Rohm and Haas) by distilling twice at a pressure of 150 mm Hg immediately before use, while Oh-Kil-Kim¹⁰ purified MA (Eastman Organic Chemicals) by distillation. It is not clear whether different manufacturers used different stabilisers for MA.

The thermal decomposition of KPS in aqueous solutions in the presence and absence of MA in N₂-atmosphere, was carried out in a 1-liter round-bottom pyrex flask fitted with a Hg-seal stirrer, a dilatometer, and side-tubes for passing N₂ gas and for extracting solutions under N₂-pressure for analysis^{11,12}. If the polymer was a precipitate under the experimental conditions, the reaction was carried out in 250-ml conical flasks⁵⁻⁷. To avoid complications during polymerizations and also during the thermal decomposition of KPS, no buffer solutions were used. Traces of metal ions present in the buffer ingredients, were found to accelerate the rate of KPS decomposition. In the pH range of 3–7, H⁺ ions have no measurable effect on the rates of KPS decompositions¹³. Undecomposed KPS was estimated by the iodometric method of Kolthoff and Carr¹³. The polymerization of MA in aqueous solution was studied in N₂-atmosphere and was followed as a function of time by the conventional gravimetric method⁵⁻⁷. Molecular weights of the polymers were measured by the viscometric method^{9,14}.

Results and Discussion

The results of persulphate decompositions in aqueous solutions in the presence and absence of MA, are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. Fig. 1 shows undecomposed persulphate as a function of time in the presence and absence of MA. It is evident that MA has accelerated the rates of persulphate decompositions, and in a given run in the presence of MA, the rates of persulphate decompositions were found to decrease with time or with the conversion of monomer to polymer (Fig. 1).

In Fig. 2, the rates of persulphate decompositions as a functions of time are shown at a given concentrations of persulphate (1.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³) and at various concentrations of the monomer (0.133–0.531 mol dm⁻³). It is found empirically that the time average rates decrease approximately linearly with time at a given concentration

of monomer and of initiator. By extrapolating the resulting straight line to zero time (Fig. 2),

Fig. 1. Effect of monomer (MA) on the thermal decomposition of potassium persulphate (2.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³) in aqueous solution at 50° in presence of nitrogen: (A) in absence of MA and (B) in presence of MA (0.3985 mol dm⁻³).

Fig. 2. Effect of monomer concentrations on the time average rates of persulphate decomposition; rates are plotted as a function of time; (A) 0.5313, (B) 0.3985, (C) 0.2656, and (D) 0.1328 mol dm⁻³ MA; initial concentration of K₂S₂O₈ = 10⁻² mol dm⁻³.

the initial rates of persulphate decompositions at various monomer concentrations were obtained. In Fig. 3, log (rate) vs log [MA] was plotted, and the slope of the line 1.15 gives the order of the monomer with respect to the persulphate decomposition. Fig. 4 shows the rate of persulphate decomposition at a given concentration of MA (0.398 mol dm⁻³) and at various concentrations of the persulphate (0.50–2.0) × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³. The order of persulphate was found to be about 1.42 (Fig. 5) with respect to its decomposition. The results of Figs. 3 and 5 show clearly that,

$$-d(S_2O_8^{2-})/dt \propto (S_2O_8^{2-})^{1.42} \times (M)^{1.15}$$

which is not consistent with the assumed mechanism stated in the introduction.

Fig. 3. Plot of \log_{10} (initial rate) of persulphate decomposition (in $\text{mol dm}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$) against \log_{10} (monomer concentration) (in mol dm^{-3}).

Fig. 5. Order plot of the persulphate with respect to persulphate decomposition in presence of MA; plot of \log_{10} (initial rate of persulphate decomposition in $\text{mol dm}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$) vs \log_{10} (concentration of persulphate in mol dm^{-3}).

Fig. 4. Plots of time-average rates of persulphate decompositions vs time; $[\text{MA}] = 0.3985 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8]$ in $\times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$: (A) 2.0, (B) 1.0, (C) 0.75 and (D) 0.50.

Table 1 shows the formation of polymer as a function of time, and the molecular weights of the polymer formed. The polymer was found to be soluble in common solvents, viz. benzene, toluene and acetone, and this suggests that no cross-linked polymers were formed even when the initial concentration of persulphate was fairly high (about

TABLE 1—MOLECULAR WEIGHTS AND INTRINSIC VISCOSITY OF POLYMETHYL ACRYLATE IN BENZENE AT 30°

Recipe: $[\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8] = 2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{MA}] = 39.8 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 50°, Ionic strength = 0.15 (adjusted by adding K_2SO_4)

Time min	Percent conversion to polymer	Huggin's constant, K_h	Average K_h	Intrinsic viscosity, η , dl g^{-1}	\bar{M}_v^* $\times 10^{-6}$
5	11.6	0.43	0.402 ± 0.05	3.27	1.27
15	50.0	0.37		2.54	0.92
30	71.0	0.45		2.27	0.80
80	81.2	0.36		1.95	0.66

*The equation used to find out the molecular weight of the polymer¹⁴: $[\eta] = 4.59 \times 10^{-5} \times (\bar{M}_v)^{0.795}$.

($10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$). Table 2 shows the change of pH of the medium as a function of time during the decomposition of persulphate (initial concentration $1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$). pH has also been calculated from the amount of persulphate decomposed and it is based on the assumption⁶,

and,

TABLE 2 CHANGE OF pH OF THE MEDIUM AS A FUNCTION OF TIME*

Time min	[S ₂ O ₈ ²⁻] decomposed (A) × 10 ⁻⁴ mol dm ⁻³	(ΔH ⁺) _t from (A) × 10 ⁴ g-ion dm ⁻³	(H ⁺) _∞ - (H ⁺) ₀ + (ΔH ⁺) _t × 10 ⁴ (B)	pH Calcd. from (B)	pH Exptl. ± 0.05
0	0.0	0.00	0.063 1	5.20	5.20
30	0.31	0.62	0.683 1	4.17	4.05
60	0.62	1.24	1.303 1	3.88	3.80
90	0.92	1.84	1.903 1	3.72	3.65
120	1.23	2.46	2.523 1	3.59	3.56

*Initial [K₂S₂O₈] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, pH = 5.2 at t = 0 and this gave (H⁺)₀ = 0.631 × 10⁻⁵ g-ion dm⁻³ and k₁ = 1.71 × 10⁻⁶ s⁻¹ at 50°.

The agreement between the calculated and estimated values of pH of the medium seems to be quite satisfactory considering the experimental errors involved in measuring the undecomposed persulphate as a function of time and also in pH measurements. Table 3 shows the estimated initial rates of persulphate decomposition at 50° in N₂-atmosphere at various concentrations of persulphate and of monomer. Ionic strength of the medium was kept constant by adding K₂SO₄ wherever required. The initial rates were higher at higher monomer and higher initiator concentrations.

TABLE 3 - ESTIMATED INITIAL RATES OF PERSULPHATE DECOMPOSITION FROM FIGS 2 AND 4 AT 50° IN NITROGEN ATMOSPHERE

[K ₂ S ₂ O ₈] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	[MA] mol dm ⁻³	[K ₂ SO ₄] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	(Initial rate of K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ decomposition) × 10 ⁹ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹
1.00	0.531 3	0.00	30.23
1.00	0.398 5	0.00	20.03
1.00	0.265 6	0.00	12.00
1.00	0.132 8	0.00	10.00
2.00	0.398 5	3.00	52.20
1.00	0.398 5	4.00	22.20
0.75	0.398 5	4.25	12.00
0.50	0.398 5	4.50	7.20

The enhanced rates of persulphate decompositions in the presence of MA could not be explained by the very simple mechanism stated earlier. The following elementary reactions are found to give a quantitative description of persulphate decomposition in aqueous solution in N₂-atmosphere and in the presence of MA.

Reactions (1), (2) and (3) are the accepted mechanism of persulphate decomposition^{1,2,7} in aqueous solution (pH 4-7). It is believed that in the presence of reactive monomers all the SO₄^{·-} radicals are believed to disappear via the reaction (4), and consequently reactions (2) and (3) are suppressed^{1,2}. (M_j)_w is a water-soluble oligomeric free radical present in the aqueous phase as well as in the latex particles. If i = j, then M_i and M_j radicals are the same. It is assumed that if i or j > 10, the radicals would be insoluble in water.

and would be found only in the polymer phase, and k_p is independent of polymer chain-length¹⁸.

Reaction (5) is also an initiation reaction in the aqueous phase due to the reduction activation of the monomer by the persulphate ions⁵⁻⁷. Reaction (8) takes account of the chain transfer to monomer either in the aqueous or in the polymer phase. Reaction (9) shows the distribution of polymeric and oligomeric free radicals between the polymer phase (subscript, p) and aqueous phase (subscript, w). It is assumed that the free radicals, M_1 and R' from the reaction (8) are chemically indistinguishable. Reaction (10) shows that a fraction of the water-soluble free radicals are oxidised by the persulphate ions in the aqueous phase. Reaction (11) takes into consideration the distribution of monomer between the polymer phase and the aqueous phase during the reaction. Reactions (12) and (13) give the termination reactions in the aqueous phase and polymer phase respectively.

From the proposed reaction model, it is evident that

$$-d(S_2O_8^{2-})/dt = k_1(S_2O_8^{2-}) + k_5(S_2O_8^{2-})(M) + k_{10}(M)_w(S_2O_8^{2-}) \quad (i)$$

Rate of initiation in the aqueous phase, $(R_i)_w$, is given by

$$(R_i)_w = [2k_1 + 2k_5(M) + k_{10}(M)_w](S_2O_8^{2-})V_w \quad (ii)$$

Assuming that (1) and (5) are the major chain initiation reactions, and neglecting (10), we get,

$$(R_i)_w = [2k_1 + 2k_5(M)](S_2O_8^{2-})V_w \quad (iii)$$

where V_w is volume fraction of the aqueous phase and V_p the volume fraction of the polymer phase, that is, $V_w + V_p = 1.0$. Under the experimental conditions, $V_w \gg V_p$, or $V_w \times 1.0$. Rate of termination in the aqueous phase, $(R_t)_w$, is given by

$$(R_t)_w = 2k_{tw}(M)_w^2 V_w \quad (iv)$$

Equating equations (iii) and (iv) in the steady state, we get,

$$(M)_w = k_{tw}^{-\frac{1}{2}} [k_1 + k_5(M)]^{\frac{1}{2}} (S_2O_8^{2-})^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (v)$$

Combining equations (i) and (v), we get,

$$1/(S_2O_8^{2-}) \{-d(S_2O_8^{2-})/dt\} = k_1 + k_5(M) + k_{10}k_{tw}^{-\frac{1}{2}} [k_1 + k_5(M)]^{\frac{1}{2}} (S_2O_8^{2-})^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (vi)$$

Equation (vi) predicts that the orders of MA and of persulphate would be greater than unity, which are consistent with the results presented here. Further, the left-hand-side of equation (vi) has been plotted against $(S_2O_8^{2-})^{\frac{1}{2}}$, at a given concentration of the monomer (Fig. 6). The data are somewhat scattered possibly due to the experimental error. From the slope and intercept of the resulting straight line by the least-square method, we get

$k_{10}^2/k_{tw} = 2.75 \times 10^{-8} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Taking k_{tw} as $3.70 \times 10^6 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ from Banerjee *et al.*¹¹, we get k_{10} as $1.06 \times 10^2 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 50°. From the intercept of Fig. 6, we get $k_5 = 1.23 \times 10^{-5} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, taking $(M) = 0.3985 \text{ (mol/dm}^3)$ and $k_1 = 1.70 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$ from this work and also from Banerjee *et al.*¹⁰. From the data of undecomposed persulphate as a function of time in the absence of MA (Fig. 1), it is found that

$$-d(S_2O_8^{2-})/dt = k_1(S_2O_8^{2-})$$

and the estimated value of k_1 was found to be $1.71 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$, which agrees very well with the literature values^{15-17,19}.

Fig. 6. Plot of $1/(S_2O_8^{2-}) \times \{-d(S_2O_8^{2-})/dt\}$ vs $(S_2O_8^{2-})^{\frac{1}{2}}$ according to the equation (vi) by least-square method.

It has also been observed that the rate of persulphate decomposition decreases with time in the presence of MA or with the conversion of monomer to polymer in a given run (Fig. 1). At about 80% conversion of monomer to polymer, the rate of persulphate decomposition is approximately the same as that in the absence of MA. This fact shows that the dissolved monomer in the aqueous phase is responsible for the accelerated rates of persulphate decomposition. Further, the polymer formed is found to be soluble in common solvents (*viz.* benzene, toluene and acetone), which indicates that no cross-linked polymers were formed. This in turn suggests that the polymer is not responsible for the induced decomposition of persulphate.

We conclude that methyl acrylate accelerates the persulphate decomposition as long as it remains in the aqueous solution. The previous assumption

that water-soluble vinyl monomers such as MA, VA, EA, and AN etc., do not induce the decomposition of persulphate during their aqueous and emulsion polymerisations, is not supported by the experimental data⁶⁻⁷.

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